

Spain

This report describes the structure of the national higher education system in Spain, focusing on the institutional types as defined by national categories. It builds on the Eurydice Report on the national higher education system and complements it with quantitative information on the role of higher education institution (HEI) types in Spain, based on data derived from the European Tertiary Education Register (<http://www.eter-project.eu>) for the period 2011-2020.

Types of Higher Education Institutions

According to Eurydice¹, higher education institutions in Spain are classified according to whether they provide university or non-university education. Advanced vocational training, advanced artistic education, advanced plastic arts and design professional studies as well as advanced sports education are non-university education institutions in Spain and are therefore not included in ETER.

University education is provided by public universities on the one hand, and private universities on the other. Both public and private universities must be registered in the Register of Universities, Centres and Qualifications (RUCT), which is under the responsibility of the Ministry of Universities.

Public universities are integrating university schools, faculties, departments, university institutes for research, doctoral colleges and other schools or structures necessary for the development of their functions:

- University schools and faculties are responsible for the organisation of their studies and in charge of the academic, administrative and management processes to award the different university degrees. They also produce substantial research.
- Departments are the teaching and research units in charge of coordinating studies according to the teaching programme of the university and of supporting teaching and research activities and initiatives of the teaching staff.
- Research university institutes are centres for scientific and technical research or artistic creation. They can be set up by one or more universities, or jointly with other public or private organisations.
- Doctoral colleges organise PhD programmes and may include official Master's degree courses with a fundamentally scientific content, as well as other open research training activities.
- Public or private associated centres may offer studies leading to the award of official degrees (issued by the university) that are valid throughout the national territory.

Private universities are legal entities that elaborate and approve their own organisation and functioning regulations, following the Spanish legislation and accreditation for universities, degrees, etc. Private universities must respect and guarantee, through a broad participation of the university community, the

¹<https://eurydice.eacea.ec.europa.eu/national-education-systems/spain/types-higher-education-institutions>

academic freedom manifested in the academic, research and study freedom. The private university sector has a stronger focus on teaching than on research.

Eurydice data for the academic year 2020-2021 show that the Spanish university system comprises 84 universities:

- 50 public universities, 47 of them offering on-site teaching and 1 distance teaching. In addition, there are 2 public universities with a special status that only provide specialised postgraduate programmes (Master's and PhD).
- 34 private universities, of which 29 offer on-site teaching and 5 distance teaching.

Main institutional characteristics. Legal status and the right to award a PhD

Table 1 provides a quantitative overview of the main institutional characteristics by HEI type. Public universities (universidad pública) are the leading actors in the Spanish higher education system, and all 50 public universities have the right to award PhDs. The private university sector (universidad privada) is playing an increasing role in Spain, accounting already for about 40% of all Spanish HEIs in 2020. The largest part of private universities is also awarding PhDs (25 out of the total of 34 institutions, resulting in 74% of the private universities)².

Table 1. Institutional type and legal status by HEI type, 2020

Category	N	PhD awarding		
		N	Share	
Private university	Universidad privada	34	25	74%
Public university	Universidad pública	50	50	100%
Total		84	74	88%

Institutional history. Older and younger institutional types

Data on the HEI foundation year provide information on the history of higher education in Spain and the evolution of its public and private sectors over time.

Figure 1 indicates the ancient historical roots of the Spanish university system in terms of the number of HEIs. Starting with the University of Salamanca, the oldest Spanish university dating back to 1218, a total of 10 HEIs were founded before the 18th century. Then, for more than two centuries, the number of both public and private HEIs remained rather stable, with the establishment of only 7 new HEIs. In the 1970s, a new dynamic

² In the preceding report, 25 out of 34 private universities were classified as PhD-awarding in 2019. For 2020, the present report finds only 25 PhD-rewarding institutions.

started with an expansion of the university sector. From the 1970s until the 1990s, the number of public HEIs has more than tripled, resulting in 50 institutions in 1998. Since then, no public universities have been founded in Spain. The private university sector started a similar expansion two decades later, resulting in 34 private universities in 2015, and levelling off since then.

Figure 1. Foundation year of HEIs by type

Students

In contrast to the number of institutions, public universities (*universidad pública*) still account for the lion share of all enrolled students in 2020 (almost 80% of all students). On the other hand, while almost 40% of Spanish HEIs are private universities (*universidad privada*), they account only for about 22% of the enrolled students, and thus play a limited role in the national higher education system (see Figure 2).

This still dominant role of the public universities is observed at all educational levels. However, we can still observe systematic differences in enrolment between educational levels: Private universities have their strength especially in Master-level education, they account for 43% of all Master students (ISCED7) and 24% of the long degree Master students in Spain (without intermediate Bachelor's degree). In comparison, their share of Bachelor Students (ISCED6) is only 17%.

In a changing educational landscape, the remaining specific asset of the public university sector in Spain is the awarding of doctoral degrees. The 50 public universities account for 94% of the PhD students, while only about 6% of the doctoral students are enrolled in one of the 25 PhD-awarding private universities.

Figure 2. Students by level and type of HEI, 2020

Personnel

People are a core resource for HEIs, as their competences are essential for teaching, undertaking research and producing scientific output. In that respect, ETER provides a rich set of data moving beyond the information available in EUROSTAT, which allows to analyse the composition of personnel by type of HEI and characteristics such as gender, nationality, educational field and, from 2020 onwards, by levels of seniority.

As illustrated in Figure 3, in the year 2020, public universities account for 86% of the academic personnel in the Spanish HEI system, and only 14% of the academic personnel refers to private universities. This corresponds to the fact that, on the one hand, public universities are much larger than private universities: The 50 public universities have about 1,650 (FTE) academic personnel on average, while the 33 private universities employ only 365 (FTE) academic personnel. On the other hand, private universities have a stronger focus on education: more than 22% of the total enrolled students, but only 14% of the academic personnel (FTE) refer to private universities. Similar relations refer to research assistants (94% are employed in public and only 6% in private universities).

Figure 3. Personnel (FTE) by category and type of HEI, 2020

Since the data collection 2020, ETER also includes information on academic staff seniority level based on a classification jointly developed by OECD and EUROSTAT³. Combined with information on gender, this information allows measuring two critical issues, i.e., career prospects of academic staff and the so-called leaky pipeline, i.e. the fact that the share of female academic staff decreases systematically with seniority levels.

As for Spain, head count (HC) data are available for public universities by four levels of seniority of the academic personnel (Junior, Intermediate, Senior and Other), while for private universities there are only data available for Junior, Intermediate and Other academic personnel⁴. Taking this caveat into account, Figure 4 reflects the leaky pipeline for female academic staff in public and private Spanish universities. While females represent 47% of total junior academic staff, their share decreases to 45% at the level of intermediate academic personnel, and drops sharply to 26% at the level of senior academic staff. Other academic personnel is female at a rate of 44%.

³ OECD (2022), Education at a Glance, Paris, pp. 412-413.

⁴ By definition, the highest level of seniority in Spanish private universities (Catedrático of Private University) is classified as Intermediate, while full professors in public universities (Catedrático of Public University) rank as Senior.

Figure 4. Academic personnel by seniority level and gender (HC), 2020

A final important dimension is internationality since it is generally considered as beneficial for the quality of research and education. In ETER, this is measured by the share of academic personnel not having the citizenship of the country ('foreigners'). As shown in Figure 5, the last decade (from 2011-20) has seen a strong increase in internationality of the Spanish university sector, as the share of foreign academic personnel is concerned. Hereby, the private universities are more international, having increased the share of foreign academic personnel from 4.7% in 2011 to 6.3% in 2020. This process of internationalisation, however, has started from a generally very low level, especially in the public university sector, which still lags way behind, with a share of 3.4% foreign academic personnel in 2020. As compared with other European countries, the Spanish universities are among the least internationalised in that respect.

Figure 5. Share of foreign academic personnel (HC) by type of HEI, 2011 and 2020

Changing roles over time

When observed through the lens of the number of enrolled students in Spain, data show a pattern of slight decrease in the overall number of students from 2011 to 2016, followed by a subsequent gentle increase until 2020 (Figure 6). The overall decline was basically caused by a decline in enrolment at public universities (which levelled off since 2016). In contrast, enrolment at private universities in Spain has risen by 50% in the

observation period, leading to a continuous and substantial shift of students from public to private universities in the Spanish HEI system.

Figure 6. Students enrolled by type of HEI, 2011-2020

As shown by Figure 7, the number of academic personnel (FTE) in Spanish universities is rather stable, whereby minor changes are following the number of enrolled students. Hereby, the slow overall growth (9% from 2011 to 2020) is mainly due to an increase in the private university sector, which grew by 50% in terms of academic personnel. In the case of public universities, Figure 7 shows the impact of the economic crisis of 2008 in their hiring possibilities. This crisis carried with it mandates that, among other measures, established heavy limitations in the replacement rate of the staff at public institutions – including universities. Accordingly, their academic staff steadily decreased up to 2014. In 2015, public universities found a way to recover their hiring ability and provided academics with employment and promotion prospects, while in 2017 the situation started to stabilise.

Figure 7. Academic personnel (FTE) by type of HEI, 2011-2020

twitter.com/eter_eu

www.eter-project.eu

eter@eter-project.eu

Università
della
Svizzera
italiana

JOANNEUM
RESEARCH
POLICIES

AUSTRIAN INSTITUTE
OF TECHNOLOGY

NIFU

Nordisk institutt for studier av
innovasjon, forskning og utdanning

SAPIENZA
UNIVERSITÀ DI ROMA